

**PEDAGOGICAL MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS PHYSICAL
EDUCATION IN HIGH SCHOOL****Musayev Zarifjon Tursunaliyevich**

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the identification of the most effective psychological mechanisms for managing the physical education of children, the organization of a health-preserving educational environment in a modern educational organization. Physical education in high school is more focused on the formation of a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that are used to achieve physical and intellectual development. The methodological literature on physical culture and sports presents various forms of means, technologies and techniques for improving the system of physical education in high school.

Keywords: physical education, physical culture, physical education in high school, management of the process of physical education, step-by-step formation of mental actions.

Statement of the problem in general form and its connection with important scientific and practical tasks. The physical condition and health of modern youth, indicators of their physical fitness and functional state have a steady tendency to deteriorate, due to low motor activity, as well as insufficient controllability of the process of physical education of high school students.

The state of health of high school students – future specialists is of increasing concern, since physical education classes do not compensate for the increasing shortage of muscle load; do not contribute to the formation of motivation and value attitude to physical activities, to their health; effective forms and methods of managing the process of physical education of high school students have not been developed.

Thus, the main task of an educational organization is to ensure an active, conscious, solid and systematic assimilation of the basics of sciences by students, as a result of which they acquire various skills and abilities. This also applies directly to physical education and sports classes, so that children master universal educational activities aimed at forming the ability to meaningfully apply theoretical knowledge when performing practical tasks.

Of course, it is wrong to consider it an absolutely uncontrollable, spontaneously developing process, since this contradicts the definition of education as a purposeful process. However, the fact that physical education is

organized, directed and directed by a teacher does not mean that it represents a sufficiently controlled and regulated pedagogical process.

After all, under managed education, under all other relevant conditions, most researchers understand such a form of organization of education and upbringing, in which every achievement of children is checked, when the teacher constantly receives the necessary information about how each of the students at each stage of educational activity acquires the appropriate competencies, when they move to the study of new material only after solid assimilation the previous topic.

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After all, under managed education, under all other appropriate conditions, most researchers understand such a form of organization of education and upbringing, in which every achievement of children is checked, when the teacher constantly receives the necessary information about how each of the students at each stage of educational activity acquires the appropriate competencies, while they proceed to the study of new material only after solid assimilation of the previous topic.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the obtained scientific results. As the results of our study have shown, traditional forms and methods of conducting physical culture classes do not contribute to obtaining a full-fledged physical education, since the dominant function of physical culture remains the adjustment of classes to the standard standards of general physical fitness to increase the external indicators of the level of physical fitness of children. Of course, with this approach, the educational side of physical culture as a compulsory academic discipline suffers more often.

One of the possible ways to solve this problem, in our opinion, is a specially organized educational and cognitive activity based on the concept of P.Ya. Galperin called "theory of step-by-step formation of mental actions", based on L.S. Vygotsky's research on the psychological aspects of the specifics of the formation of mental actions. The effectiveness of this theory lies in the fact that in the ontogenesis of personality development there is an interiorization of actions, expressed in the gradual transformation of external actions into internal mental actions.

Further, due to its consistent rethinking, determination of the indicative basis of actions, generalization, partial reduction and transformation of its leading structural components, its internalization is carried out, that is, the conscious transformation of external action into internal, already proceeding entirely in the mind of the student. Hence the name "step-by-step formation of mental actions".

This concept, as noted in some studies, is not implemented implicitly by all teachers, since they believe that the consistent implementation of all these stages is not always effective. At the same time, we believe that the theory of gradual assimilation of mental actions is very effective in the process of assimilation of theoretical knowledge and their gradual implementation in practice in the process of physical education, and will also allow maximum control of the process of improving physical education of high school students. The type of orientation in the educational material is formed when high school students have not yet started to complete the task.

This is a set of recommendations on how to perform this action in practice, guided by the theoretical knowledge obtained and have an idea of the expected results. Then the high school students begin to implement it in practice. Thus, the maximum control of the process of gradual formation of mental actions for mastering theoretical knowledge was carried out, and through them the meaningful practical implementation of physical actions, that is, the performance of which physical action is necessary to strengthen and maintain the corresponding vital human organ.

We consider the technology of programmed learning to be the next direction of improving the physical education of children based on the most effective management of this process.

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